

Data Management Plan Information

Coverage of open citations in DOAJ journals

The purpose of this research is finding out the coverage of DOAJ articles in terms of citations, according to OpenCitations indexes: how many citations DOAJ journals receive and do; how many of these involve open access articles; and finally, the presence of trends over time of the availability of citations involving these articles.

Funder

None

Grant

None

Organisations

University of Bologna

Researchers

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Datasets

Title: Software for coverage of open citations in DOAJ journals

Template: Horizon 2020

The software used for gathering, manipulating and analyzing data of this research

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information, To share information, To keep on record

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?
reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?
Software

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?
Primary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?
KB (kilobyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?
Researchers, Research communities

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?
No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

- Yes
- Dublin Core
 - Dublin core for generic basic metadata, to be refined later

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

- Yes
 - Dublin Core

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?
Yes

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Linked Open Data

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

- Yes
- Python Compiled File

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

- Yes
- .py

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

- Yes
- Zenodo

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Other
- GitHub repository
- <https://github.com/open-sci/2021-2022/tree/main/docs/DonTLockUp>

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?
immediately

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

- Yes
 - All of the researchers will be data managers

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a.
Constance Dami (orcid:0000-0003-4819-3975)

b.
Chiara Manca (orcid:0000-0003-4037-1175)

c.
Umut Kucuk (orcid:0000-0002-6352-2215)

d.
Alessandro Bertozzi (orcid:0000-0003-0933-4640)

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?
Institutional archive

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?
No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?
No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?
No

Title: Dataset for the coverage of open citations in DOAJ journals

Template: Horizon 2020

The dataset contains the results for our research on the coverage of open citations in DOAJ journals. More specifically, a JSON file containing statistical informations for journals and the citations they do and receive.

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information, To share information, To keep on record, To combine with other data

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models)
- Secondary data after extraction and analyzes from OpenCitations and DOAJ data.

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files, Numerical, Specimen collections

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers, Research communities

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

- Yes
- To compare and combine with other data, To follow-up research on a specific area

2.1.2 Where do the described data reside?

Zenodo

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

- Yes
- Dublin Core
- For general metadata, to be refined later

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

- Yes

- DublinCore and more

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

- Linked Open Data

- OpenAIRE

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

No

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Other

- GitHub repository

- For now, to be defined later

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

Yes

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?
immediately

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

Yes

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

Use of tools for automatic checks, Data conform to format specification, Consistency verified with data models and standards

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

- Yes

- All of the researchers

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

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6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

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7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No